

Supplementary Table S1: Search parameters for SearchGUI to analyze clinical datasets in Galaxy. Parameters were based on instrumentation, data generation, and data analysis protocols detailed in the original publications.

Dataset Information and Search parameters	PXD019423	PXD019686	PXD020394	PXD021328	PXD022085	PXD023016	PXD024967	PXD025214	PXD026795	PXD034582
Geographical location	Germany	France	Uruguay	Brazil	China	India	USA	Brazil	USA	Brazil
Instrument used	Orbitrap Fusion Tribrid mass spectrometer	Q-Exactive HF tandem mass spectrometer	Q Exactive Plus (Q-Orbitrap) (Thermo) mass spectrometer	Q-Exactive HF-X mass spectrometer	Q Exactive HF mass spectrometer	Orbitrap Fusion Mass Spectrometer	Orbitrap Fusion Lumos Mass spectrometer	Q-Exactive HF-X mass spectrometer	Orbitrap Exploris 480 mass spectrometer	Q-Exactive HF-X mass spectrometer
Algorithms	XITandem, MS-GF+	XITandem, MS-GF+	XITandem, MS-GF+	XITandem, MS-GF+	XITandem, MS-GF+	XITandem, MS-GF+	XITandem, MS-GF+	XITandem, MS-GF+	XITandem, MS-GF+	XITandem, MS-GF+
Digestion Enzymes	Trypsin	Trypsin	Trypsin	Trypsin	Trypsin	Trypsin	Trypsin	Trypsin	Trypsin	Trypsin
Missed cleavages	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Precursor Ion Tolerance	10 ppm	5 ppm	10 ppm	20 ppm	10 ppm	10 ppm	10 ppm	20 ppm	10 ppm	5 ppm
Fragment Tolerance	0.05 Da	0.02 Da	0.05 Da	20 ppm	0.05 Da	0.05 Da	0.02 Da	20 ppm	0.02 Da	20 ppm
Minimum Charge	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Maximum Charge	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Fixed Modifications	Carbamidomethylation of C	Carbamidomethylation of C	Carbamidomethylation of C	-	Carbamidomethylation of C	Carbamidomethylation of C	Carbamidomethylation of C	Carbamidomethylation of C	Carbamidomethylation of C	Carbamidomethylation of C
Variable Modifications	Deamidation of N, Oxidation of M	Deamidation of N, Deamidation of Q, Oxidation of M	Oxidation of M	Acetylation of protein N-term, Oxidation of M	Acetylation of protein N-term, Oxidation of M	Oxidation of M	TMT-10plex of peptide N-term, TMT 10plex of Protein N term, Oxidation of M	Acetylation of protein N-term, Oxidation of M	Oxidation of M	Oxidation of M
Minimum Peptide Length	6	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
Maximum Peptide Length	30	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60
Maximum Precursor Error	10 ppm	5 ppm	10 ppm	10 ppm	10 ppm	10 ppm	10 ppm	10 ppm	10 ppm	10 ppm

Supplementary Table S2: Parameters for the PepQuery search engine for the validation of clinical datasets in Galaxy.

Search Parameters	PXD019423	PXD019686	PXD020394	PXD021328	PXD022085	PXD023016	PXD024967	PXD025214	PXD026795	PXD034582
<i>PepQuery Parameters</i>	Carbamidomethylation of C	Carbamidomethylation of C	Carbamidomethylation of C		Carbamidomethylation of C	Carbamidomethylation of C	Carbamidomethylation of C	Carbamidomethylation of C	Carbamidomethylation of C	Carbamidomethylation of C
Fixed modification(s)	Oxidation of M	Oxidation of M	Oxidation of M	Oxidation of M	Oxidation of M, Acetylation of peptide N-terminus	Oxidation of M				
Variable modification(s)	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Max Modifications	True	True	True	True	True	True	True	True	True	True
Unrestricted modification?	True	True	True	True	True	True	True	True	True	True
Amino Acid substitutions?	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Precursor tolerance	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm
Precursor unit	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05
Product tolerance (Da)	Trypsin	Trypsin	Trypsin	Trypsin	Trypsin	Trypsin	Trypsin	Trypsin	Trypsin	Trypsin
Digestion enzyme	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Max missed cleavages	CID/HCD	CID/HCD	CID/HCD	CID/HCD	CID/HCD	CID/HCD	CID/HCD	CID/HCD	CID/HCD	CID/HCD
Fragmentation	HyperScore	HyperScore	HyperScore	HyperScore	HyperScore	HyperScore	HyperScore	HyperScore	HyperScore	HyperScore

Supplementary Figure S1: Coverage of the 203 peptides obtained from the Discovery workflow to the 803 peptide panel from published data provides us with 100 unique peptides.

Supplementary Figure S2: Manual inspection of the spectra to validate peptide quality. The criteria for an accepted spectrum were that the spectra containing product ions should be at least a three-fold higher intensity than the noise level and the spectra should have at least three consecutive b- or y-ions in their series.

b+	#	Seq#	y+
58.0287	1	G 20	
186.0873	2	Q 19	2123.9992
243.1088	3	G 18	1995.9407
342.1772	4	V 17	1938.9192
439.2300	5	P 16	1839.8508
552.3140	6	I 15	1742.7980
666.3570	7	N 14	1629.7140
767.4046	8	T 13	1515.6710
881.4476	9	N 12	1414.6233
968.4796	10	S 11	1300.5804
1055.5116	11	S 10	1213.5484
1152.5644	12	P 9	1126.5164
1267.5913	13	D 8	1029.4636
1382.6183	14	D 7	914.4367
1510.6768	15	Q 6	799.4097
1623.7609	16	I 5	671.3511
1680.7824	17	G 4	558.2671
1843.8457	18	Y 3	501.2456
2006.9090	19	Y 2	338.1823
	20	R 1	175.1190

b+	#	Seq#	y+
58.0287	1	G 20	
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666.3570	7	N 14	1629.7140
767.4046	8	T 13	1515.6710
881.4476	9	N 12	1414.6233
968.4796	10	S 11	1300.5804
1055.5116	11	S 10	1213.5484
1152.5644	12	P 9	1126.5164
1267.5913	13	D 8	1029.4636
1382.6183	14	D 7	914.4367
1510.6768	15	Q 6	799.4097
1623.7609	16	I 5	671.3511
1680.7824	17	G 4	558.2671
1843.8457	18	Y 3	501.2456
2006.9090	19	Y 2	338.1823
	20	R 1	175.1190

Supplementary Table S3: Number of peptide-spectral matches (PSMs) and peptide intensities of the detected variant peptides from the 12 datasets. The PSM numbers reported here are PSMs that qualify after PepQuery analysis (PSM rank output) with a P-value of 0.05. The peptide intensity values reported in parentheses have been extracted from MaxQuant or FlashLFQ software outputs.

Variant peptides	PXD019423	PXD019686	PXD020394	PXD021328	PXD022085	PXD023016	PXD024967	PXD025214	PXD026795	PXD034582 (August2021)	PXD034582 (September 2021)	PXD034582 (January 2022)
GQGVPIINTSSR	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	6 (5.4x10 ⁹)	-	1(1.2x10 ⁷)	1 (1.7x10 ⁶)	-
AYETQALPQR	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	6 (6x10 ⁸)	-
GEGVPINTSSPDDQIGYYR	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1(8.8x10 ⁵)	1	1
SMGTSPTRMANGGDAALALLLLDR	-	-	-	1 (1.1x10 ⁷)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PGNGCDAALALLLLDR	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	2	-	-	-	-
ITFGGPSDSTG SNQNGGAR	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	7 (8.3x10 ⁶)

Supplementary Table S4: Pango lineage associated with the peptide sequences.

Peptide sequences	Peptide sequences (I=>L)	Matching status 1 = exact match 0.5 = M removed 0.2 = non-trypsinic	Closest matching peptide sequence from GISAID allprot0203 dated 2022/02/03	Protein(s)	Pango Lineage	5first+5last countries	First Accession ID	First Pango lineage	Number of Accession IDs
GEGVPINTNSSPDDQIGYYR	GEGVPLNTNSSPDDQLGYR	1	GEGVPLNTNSSPDDQLGYR	{N}	[B.1.399, B.1.2, B.1.1.214, B.1.1.7, B.1.526, AY.122, B.1.617.2, AY.43, None, AY.3, AY.33, AY.4, AY.30, AY.103, BA.1]	USA_USA_USA_USA_Japan_USA_Wales_England_South Korea_USA	EPI_ISL_1924625	B.1.399	44
ITFGGPSDSTG TGSNQDGER	LTFGGPSDSTG TGSNQDGER	1	LTFGGPSDSTG TGSNQDGER	{N}	[B.1.1.448, B.4, B.1.1.7, B.1.351, B.1.1.214, B.1.429, AY.122, B.1.1.519, P.1.17, B.1.526, P.1.14, P.1, C.37, AY.4, AY.45, AY.54, AY.25, AY.4.3, AY.26, AY.110, AY.120, AY.44, AY.103, B.1.617.2, AY.129, AY.112, AY.34.1.1, AY.125, AY.100, AY.3, AY.39.1, AY.62, AY.46, AY.90, AY.7.1, AY.33, AY.121]	South Africa_England_England_England_England_Denmark_Poland_Denmark_Denmark_Germany	EPI_ISL_509346	B.1.1.448	477

MAGDGGDA ALALLLDR	MAGDGGDA ALALLLDR	1	MAGDGGDA ALALLLDR	{N}	[B.1.422, B.1.1.216, B.1.1.7, B.1.1.28, B.1, B.1.525, Q.1, P.1, AY.43, BA.1]	Canada_Eng and_England _England_Br azil_South Africa_Germa ny_Germany_ Germany_US A	EPI_ISL_586 432	B.1.422	86
PGNGCDAAL ALLLDR	PGNGCDAAL ALLLDR	0.5	MPGNGCDA ALALLLDR	{N}	[AY.44, AY.120, AY.25, AY.103]	USA_USA_S weden_Swed en_Sweden_ USA_USA_U SA_USA_US A	EPI_ISL_384 4312	AY.44	15
SMGTSPTR MAGNGGDA ALALLLDR	SMGTSPTR MAGNGGDA ALALLLDR	0.2	NSTPGSSM GTSPTRMA GNGGDAAL ALLLDR	{N}	[B.1.617.2, AY.9, AY.51, AY.9.2]	England_Port ugal_Greece_ Germany_Sw eden_Englan d_Portugal_G reece_Germa ny_Sweden	EPI_ISL_179 0832	B.1.617.2	5
LVDPQIQLAV TR	LVDPQLQLA VTR	1	LVDPQLQLA VTR	{NSP16, N}	[None, B.4.2, B.1.1, B.1.1.101, B.1.595, B.1, B.1.2, B.1.564, B.1.580, B.1.221.1, B.1.177.56, B.1.525, B.1.214.2, B.1.400, B.1.36, B.1.617.1, B.1.1.7, Q.1, B.1.36.1, B.1.177.82, R.1, B.1.177, B.1.351, B.1.160, B.1.36.29, AY.125, B.1.147, P.1.15, AY.5, B.1.429, B.1.126, B.1.617.2, AY.122, AY.4, AY.44, AY.119, BA.1, BA.1.1]	Italy_Saudi Arabia_Engla nd_Brazil_Ind ia_USA_USA_ USA_USA_ USA	EPI_ISL_414 599	None	169
NSTPGSSM GTSPAR	NSTPGSSM GTSPAR	1	NSTPGSSM GTSPAR	{N}	[B.1.617.2, B.1, AY.26, B.1.617.1, AY.23, B.1.503, AY.34.1, B, B.1.2, AY.119, None, AY.39, B.1.441, B.1.36, B.1.282, AY.44, B.1.112, AY.3, AY.103, AY.25, B.1.189, AY.67, B.1.1.432, AY.25.1, B.1.459, B.1.497, AY.1, AY.118, AY.119.2, AY.100,	France_Switz erland_Switze rland_Switzerl and_Switzerla nd_Poland_P oland_Poland _Poland_Pola nd	EPI_ISL_736 0393	B.1.617.2	3854981

					AY.81, AY.24, AY.122, AY.62, AY.54, AY.33, AY.4, AY.3.1, AY.9.2, B.1.609, AY.45, AY.82, B.1.380, B.1.36.18, AY.29, AY.112, AY.129, AY.36, AY.43, AY.4.2.3, AY.125, AY.41, B.1.177, AY.16, AY.46.3, AY.42, AY.75, AY.98.1, B.1.36.8, B.1.177.75, AY.5, B.1.177.10, B.1.160, B.1.177.73, AY.17, B.1.1.306, B.1.234, AY.72, AY.113, B.1.177.18, B.1.1, AY.120.1, B.1.617.3, B.1.525, B.1.1.318, AY.9, AY.10, B.1.1.7, AY.98, AY.8, AY.46, AY.127, AY.70, AY.93, AY.46.1, AY.55, AY.111, AY.59, AY.13, AY.15, AY.6, AY.120, AY.61, AY.77, AY.87, AY.30, AY.7, AY.4.8, AY.106, AY.92, ...]				
GQGVPIINTN SSR	GQGVPLNTN SSR	1	GQGVPLNTN SSR	{N}	[B.6.6, B.1.1.161, P.1, B.1, B.1.1.33, C.13, P.1.10, P.1.13, P.1.15, B.1.1.306, D.2, B.1.177, P.1.14, B.1.367, B.1.36, None, B.1.221, P.1.12, B.1.398, P.1.1, P.1.17, P.1.16, B.1.630, P.1.2, B.1.429, B.1.111, B.1.177.35, B.1.1, B.1.2,	bat_Thailand _USA_Englan d_USA_Germ any_England _Brazil_Engla nd_Brazil	EPI_ISL_412 977	B.6.6	112244

					<p>B.1.596, B.1.160, P.1.7.1, B.1.566, B.1.1.28, B.1.234, B.1.1.7, P.1.9, B.1.177.73, B.1.351, P.1.3, B.1.497, P.1.7, P.1.4, P.1.6, P.1.10.1, B, B.1.524, P.1.17.1, P.1.5, B.1.1.348, B.1.526, C.37, B.1.1.117, Q.8, AY.35, 0, B.1.623, B.1.1.507, P.1.8, B.1.575, B.1.399, B.1.1.54, P.1.11, B.1.533, B.1.1.519, P.1.10.2, P.7, P.4, B.1.1.222, AY.129, A.2.5, B.1.1.178, B.1.620, C.1.2, AY.68, B.1.1.265, C.36.3.1, A.2.5.3, B.1.1.307, B.1.1.317, B.1.1.121, AY.44, AY.43, B.1.1.409, B.1.617.2, AY.63, P.1.12.1, AY.39, AY.5, C.37.1, AY.112, AY.4.5, AY.47, AY.103, AY.39.1, AY.125, AY.124, AY.3, AY.26, AY.4, ...]</p>				
ITFGGPSDS TGSNQNGG AR	LTFGGPSDS TGSNQNGG AR	1	LTFGGPSDS TGSNQNGG AR	{N}	<p>[BA.1, BA.1.1, None, BA.2, B.1.1, BA.3, AY.43, AY.113, AY.44, 0, AY.45, B.1.617.2, AY.39, AY.23, AY.122, B.1.1.294, AY.127, AY.3, C.36.3, AY.75, AY.36, AY.126, AY.118, B.1.623, AY.100, AY.117,</p>	<p>England_Cze ch Republic_US A_USA_USA _Poland_Pola nd_Poland_P oland_Poland</p>	EPI_ISL_898 9562	BA.1	752651

					AY.103, AY.112, AY.125, AY.98.1, AY.25.1, AY.46.6, B.1, AY.4.7, AY.116, B.1.639, AY.20, AY.25, AY.98, P.1, AY.119, C.36.3.1, B.1.1.263, P.1.12, B.1.1.1, B.1.367, B, A, AY.79, AY.9.2, AY.1, B.1.619, C.37.1, AY.46, AY.4, B.1.1.161, AY.107, AY.121, AY.114]				
AYETQALPQ R	AYETQALPQ R	1	AYETQALPQ R	{N}	[B.1.1.514, B.1.177, AD.2, B.1.258.3, B.1.1.216, B.1.184, B.1.1, B.1.2, B.1.367, B, B.1.617.2, AY.26, B.1.617.1, A.2, AY.23, B.1, A.5, A.11, B.1.400, B.1.110.3, AY.34.1, B.29, B.1.1.71, B.4.2, B.1.428, B.1.1.28, B.1.1.87, B.1.1.33, B.1.1.222, B.1.391, B.1.8, B.1.214, AY.119, B.1.1.464, B.1.1.339, B.1.390, B.1.279, B.1.335, B.1.1.409, B.1.620, B.1.1.521, A, B.1.1.366, B.1.600, B.1.195, B.1.1.86, B.1.162, C.36, B.1.36, B.1.1.25, AY.39, AE.1, B.1.443, B.1.1.368, B.1.1.326, B.1.1.37, B.1.243, B.1.1.301, B.1.22, B.1.1.306, AY.44, AY.3, AY.103,	Greece_Engl and_Wales_E ngland_india_ Slovakia_Pol and_Mexico_ Poland_Polan d	EPI_ISL_109 6987	B.1.1.514	3935774

					B.1.546, B.1.595, B.1.1.54, AY.25, B.1.450, AY.67, B.1.1.1, B.1.509, B.1.1.291, B.1.558, B.1.404, B.1.401, B.1.609, B.1.1.70, B.1.366, B.1.369, None, B.1.206, AY.25.1, B.1.556, B.1.570, B.1.567, B.1.36.35, B.1.497, B.1.36.19, B.1.305, B.1.1.288, B.1.459, AY.1, AY.118, B.1.1.284, AY.119.2, B.1.1.198, B.1.580, AY.100, B.1.313, AY.81, ...]				
KAYETQALP QR	KAYETQALP QR	1	KAYETQALP QR	{N}	[B.1.258.3, B.1.367, B, B.1.177, AD.2, B.1.2, B.1.1.216, B.1.184, B.1.1.514, B.1.1, B.1.617.2, AY.26, B.1.617.1, A.2, AY.23, B.1, A.5, A.11, B.1.400, B.1.110.3, AY.34.1, B.29, B.1.1.71, B.4.2, B.1.428, B.1.1.28, B.1.1.87, B.1.1.33, B.1.1.222, B.1.391, B.1.8, B.1.214, AY.119, B.1.1.464, B.1.1.339, B.1.390, B.1.279, B.1.1.409, B.1.335, B.1.620, B.1.1.521, A, B.1.1.366, B.1.195, B.1.600, B.1.1.86, B.1.162, C.36, B.1.36, B.1.1.25,	England_Engl and_France_ England_Net herlands_Pol and_Poland_ Mexico_Polan d_Poland	EPI_ISL_163 7200	B.1.258.3	3930635

					AE.1, AY.39, B.1.443, B.1.1.368, B.1.1.37, B.1.1.326, B.1.243, B.1.1.301, B.1.22, B.1.1.306, AY.44, AY.3, AY.103, B.1.595, B.1.546, B.1.1.54, AY.25, B.1.450, AY.67, B.1.1.291, B.1.1.1, B.1.509, B.1.558, B.1.401, B.1.404, B.1.609, B.1.1.70, B.1.366, B.1.369, None, B.1.206, AY.25.1, B.1.556, B.1.570, B.1.36.35, B.1.567, B.1.36.19, B.1.497, B.1.305, B.1.1.288, B.1.459, AY.1, AY.118, B.1.1.284, AY.119.2, B.1.1.198, B.1.580, B.1.313, AY.100, AY.81, ...]				
QYNTQAFGR	QYNTQAFGR	1	QYNTQAFGR	{N}	[B.1.177, D.2, B.1.240.1, B.1.240, None, B.6.6, B.1, B.1.210, B.1.36, B.1.36.17]	bat_bat_bat_pangolin_pangolin_bat_bat_bat_bat_bat	EPI_ISL_852604	B.1.177	27
GPEQTQGNFGDQELTR	GPEQTQGNFGDQELTR	1	GPEQTQGNFGDQELTR	{N}	[B.1.1.33, B.1.1, N.2, None, N.6, B.1, N.1, N.4, N.3, N.5, B.1.499, C.27, N.7, N.8, B.1.91, B.1.1.332, B.1.2, B.1.139, AK.1, N.9, B.1.177.51, B.1.1.303, B.1.243, B.1.1.70, B.1.258, C.16, B.1.1.362, B.1.160.16, B.1.1.7, N.10, BA.1, B.1.429,	Brazil_Brazil_Brazil_Brazil_England_England_Denmark_England	EPI_ISL_1181624	B.1.1.33	4804

					<p>B.1.1.448, B.4, B.1.160, B.1.1.393, B.1.177, B.1.36.18, B.1.221, B.1.517, P.1, B.1.1.294, BA.1.1, B.1.177.75, B.1.177.44, B.1.609, B.1.526, B.1.404, B.1.351, B.1.1.369, B.1.1.318, AZ.5, P.1.1, P.1.12, B.1.617.2, AY.4, B.1.466.2, AY.3, AY.117, B.1.1.1, AY.2, AY.98.1, AY.44, AY.26, AY.47, AY.20, AY.29, AY.13, AY.68, AY.75, AY.25.1, AY.43, B.1.621, AY.39.1, AY.122, AY.25, AY.39, AY.103, AY.42, AY.102, AY.9.2, AY.73, AY.126, AY.99, AY.112, AY.46.2, AY.46.1, AY.23, AY.34.2, AY.98, AY.4.2.2, AY.43.3, AY.121.1, AY.4.2, AY.121, BA.2]</p>				
RGPEQTQG NFGDQELTR	RGPEQTQG NFGDQELTR	1	RGPEQTQG NFGDQELTR	{N}	<p>[B.1.1.33, B.1.1, N.2, None, N.6, B.1, N.1, N.4, N.3, N.5, B.1.499, C.27, N.7, N.8, B.1.91, B.1.1.332, B.1.2, B.1.139, AK.1, N.9, B.1.177.51, B.1.1.303, B.1.243, B.1.1.70, B.1.258, C.16, B.1.1.362, B.1.160.16, B.1.1.7, N.10, BA.1, B.1.429, B.1.1.448, B.4, B.1.160, B.1.1.393,</p>	<p>Brazil_Brazil_ Brazil_Brazil_ Brazil_Englan d_England_E ngland_Denm ark_England</p>	EPI_ISL_118 1624	B.1.1.33	4804

					B.1.177, B.1.36.18, B.1.221, B.1.517, P.1, B.1.1.294, BA.1.1, B.1.177.75, B.1.177.44, B.1.609, B.1.526, B.1.404, B.1.351, B.1.1.369, B.1.1.318, AZ.5, P.1.1, P.1.12, B.1.617.2, AY.4, B.1.466.2, AY.3, AY.117, B.1.1.1, AY.2, AY.98.1, AY.44, AY.26, AY.47, AY.20, AY.29, AY.13, AY.68, AY.75, AY.25.1, AY.43, B.1.621, AY.39.1, AY.122, AY.25, AY.39, AY.103, AY.42, AY.102, AY.9.2, AY.73, AY.126, AY.99, AY.112, AY.46.2, AY.46.1, AY.23, AY.34.2, AY.98, AY.4.2.2, AY.43.3, AY.121.1, AY.4.2, AY.121, BA.2]				
IIWVATEGAL LNTPK	LLWVATEGA LNTPK	1	LLWVATEGA LNTPK	{N}	[B.1.2]	USA_USA	EPI_ISL_108 0160	B.1.2	1
GQGVPIINTN SSPDDQIGY	GQGVPLNTN SSPDDQLGY	1	GQGVPLNTN SSPDDQLGY	{N}	[B.1.177, B.1.1.7]	Sweden_Bulg aria_Sweden _Bulgaria	EPI_ISL_240 8682	B.1.177	2
NTNSSPDDQ IGYYR	NTNSSPDDQ LGYYR	1	NTNSSPDDQ LGYYR	{N}	[BA.1.1, BA.1, B.1.1.7, AY.122, AY.43, AY.93]	England_Engl and_England _England_En gland_Spain_ Germany_Ge rmany_USA_ USA	EPI_ISL_824 2277	BA.1.1	36